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IMPACT OF CULTURAL DIFFERENCES IN PRAGMATIC USE OF WORD COMBINATIONS

Annotation

This article presents the essential theme about relation between culture and pragmatics. Mostly in article pragmatic elements, cross cultural communication with word combinations and impact of culture on various spheres widely discussed. Pragmatic and cultural competence are closely related, and both require learners to "use language in socioculturally appropriate ways" . One of the knottiest considerations in teaching L2 pragmatics is that socio-culturally and contextually appropriate (or inappropriate) communication can take a number of forms, e.g., there can be many pragmatically appropriate ways to ask for information or schedule an appointment.

Key words:pragmatic inference,interlocutor,intercultural communication, indirectness, directness,cultural taboos,pragmatic elements

Introduction

Pragmatics varies across different cultures due to factors such as conversational inference, culture, and language structure. Different languages have different word orders, which affect how speakers interpret context and make pragmatic inferences. For example, speakers of languages with an adjective-noun order integrate context by first identifying properties, while speakers of languages with a noun-adjective order integrate context by first identifying kinds. Additionally, intercultural communication requires the co-construction of common ground, as there may be limited shared knowledge and norms between interlocutors. In intracultural communication, commonalities and shared knowledge create a core common ground on which pragmatic understanding is built. However, in intercultural communication, interlocutors need to actively create common ground in the interactional context. Therefore, pragmatics varies across cultures based on language structure, contextual interpretation, and the need for common ground construction in intercultural communication.

Main body

Cultural differences play a significant role in shaping the pragmatic use of word combinations in communication. Here are some ways in which cultural differences impact pragmatic language use:

Politeness Norms: Different cultures have distinct norms regarding politeness in communication. Some cultures value directness and assertiveness, while others prioritize avoiding confrontation and maintaining harmony. These cultural norms influence the choice of words, tone, and style used in word combinations.

Indirectness vs. Directness: Cultural differences can be observed in the degree of directness or indirectness preferred in communication. Some cultures are more explicit in their language use, while others rely on implicit meanings and nuances. Word combinations may vary in their level of directness based on cultural conventions.

Expressing Respect and Hierarchy: Cultural beliefs about hierarchy and respect shape language use. In some cultures, the use of honorifics, formal language, and deferential expressions is essential to show respect to others. Word combinations in these cultures reflect social hierarchies and relationships among individuals.

Taboos and Sensitivities: Cultural taboos and sensitivities influence the choice of words and topics that are considered appropriate for communication. Word combinations that touch upon sensitive issues or taboo subjects may vary across cultures, with some topics being avoided or approached indirectly.

Humor and Figurative Language: Cultural differences are evident in the use of humor, sarcasm, irony, and figurative language. What may be considered humorous or acceptable in one culture may be perceived differently in another. Word combinations that rely on humor or figurative expressions may need to be contextualized within cultural norms to be understood correctly.

Overall, understanding and respecting cultural differences is essential for effective communication and the pragmatic use of word combinations. Awareness of cultural nuances helps individuals navigate diverse social interactions, avoid misunderstandings, and adapt their language use to foster successful communication across cultures.

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Nonverbal Communication: Cultural differences in nonverbal communication, such as gestures, facial expressions, and body language, also impact the pragmatic use of word combinations. Nonverbal cues often complement verbal communication and affect the interpretation of word combinations in different cultural contexts.

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Pragmatics significantly influences the relationship between language and culture. Here are some key ways in which pragmatics impacts cultural relationships:

Communication Styles: Pragmatic norms govern how language is used in specific cultural contexts. Communication styles, such as directness, indirectness, formality, and politeness, are deeply rooted in cultural values and beliefs.

Pragmatic choices in language use reflect and reinforce cultural norms, shaping the way individuals interact and convey meaning.

Social Hierarchies: Pragmatic elements like honorifics, deferential language, and politeness strategies reflect societal hierarchies and power dynamics within a culture. Language use is often influenced by cultural notions of respect, authority, and social status, shaping relationships between individuals and groups.

Cultural Norms and Values: Pragmatics is intertwined with cultural norms, values, and beliefs. The ways in which language is used to express emotions, convey information, negotiate meaning, and establish social bonds are informed by cultural practices and expectations. Pragmatic considerations are essential for understanding and interpreting communication in a culturally sensitive manner.

Taboos and Sensitivities: Pragmatic rules dictate what is considered appropriate or taboo in communication within a culture. Culturally sensitive topics, language taboos, and communication taboos influence word choices, conversational strategies, and polite forms of address. Adherence to these pragmatic norms is crucial for respectful and effective communication within a cultural context.

Language Use in Social Contexts: Pragmatics plays a vital role in shaping language use in social contexts, such as family interactions, workplace communication, and community settings. Cultural expectations regarding language register, politeness, and social hierarchies influence how individuals express themselves, negotiate meaning, and establish rapport in different social environments.

Cross-Cultural Communication: Understanding the pragmatic aspects of language is essential for successful cross-cultural communication. Awareness of cultural differences in language use, politeness strategies, indirectness, and nonverbal cues helps individuals navigate diverse cultural contexts, avoid misunderstandings, and build effective relationships across cultures.

Conclusion

Overall, pragmatics and culture are deeply interconnected, with language reflecting and shaping cultural practices, beliefs, and social relationships. By considering the pragmatic dimensions of communication within cultural contexts, individuals can enhance their intercultural competence, promote mutual understanding, and foster meaningful interactions across diverse cultural boundaries.

Understanding and respecting cultural differences is essential for effective communication and the pragmatic use of word combinations. Awareness of cultural nuances helps individuals navigate diverse social interactions, avoid misunderstandings, and adapt their language use to foster successful communication across cultures.

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